

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS ON ONLINE BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF BEAUTY & PERSONAL CARE PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT:

The rapid expansion of e-commerce has significantly influenced consumer buying behaviour, particularly in the Beauty & Personal Care (BPC) product segment. The present study aims to examine the impact of selected demographic factors—age, gender, education, profession, marital status, family income & place of residence—on the online buying behaviour of Beauty & Personal Care products in Madhya Pradesh. The study was conducted in Indore city, Madhya Pradesh, with a sample of 150 respondents who regularly purchase BPC products through online platforms. Simple random sampling was adopted for selecting respondents. Primary data were collected using a structured five-point Likert scale questionnaire, while secondary data were sourced from books, journals, research articles & online publications. The collected data were analyzed using regression analysis with the help of MS Excel & statistical tools.

The results reveal that demographic variables collectively have a significant impact on online buying behaviour. The regression model exhibited strong explanatory power, explaining 88.1% of the variance in the dependent variable. Education, profession, marital status, income & age were found to be significant predictors, whereas gender did not show a significant influence. The findings led to the rejection of the null hypothesis, confirming that demographic characteristics play a meaningful role in shaping online purchasing behaviour for Beauty & Personal Care products. The study provides useful insights for marketers & online retailers to design targeted strategies based on demographic profiles. However, the results are limited to a selected city & sample size, indicating scope for further research across broader geographical regions.

Keywords: *demographic factors, cosmetics, beauty products, online selling.*

INTRODUCTION:

Beauty & Personal Care (BPC) products are a diverse category of consumer goods aimed at enhancing physical appearance, maintaining personal hygiene & promoting overall well-being. Demographic factors such as youth, working professionals & urban consumers play a key role in shaping demand. These products are closely linked with lifestyle, self-image & cultural values, making them an essential part of daily life across different demographic groups.

The term **‘Beauty Products’** refers to cosmetics or materials made & sold for the purpose of enhancing the physical attractiveness of users. The term beauty products is often synonymously used with cosmetics & includes preparations applied externally to change or enhance the beauty of skin, hair, nails, lips & eyes. **‘Personal Care products’** & services includes products for the hair, oral hygiene products, shaving needs, cosmetics & bath products. According to the Food Administration Department, some "personal care products" meet the definitions of both cosmetics & drugs. This may happen when a product has two intended uses. For example, a shampoo is a cosmetic because its intended use is to cleanse the hair. An antidandruff treatment is a drug because its intended use is to treat dandruff. Consequently, an antidandruff shampoo is both a cosmetic & a drug, because it is intended to cleanse the hair & treat dandruff. Among other cosmetic/drug combinations are toothpastes that contain fluoride, deodorants that are also antiperspirants & moisturizers & makeup marketed with sun-protection claims. Such products must comply with the requirements for both cosmetics & drugs.

(Market Directory: Source <https://www.statista.com/>)

Consumer Behavior is the fundamental process of consumer psychology, which plays an important role in understanding how consumer make buying decision, though it is offline or online purchase it depends on consumer. “Consumer behavior is the study of how individuals, groups & organizations select, buy, use & dispose of goods, services, ideas, or experiences to satisfy their needs & wants (Kotler & Keller, 2011)”. “Schiffman defines consumer buying behavior as “the behavior that consumes display in searching for, purchasing, using, evaluating & disposing of products & services that they expect will satisfy their needs”. “Consumer behavior is the study of the process involved when individuals or groups select, purchase, use or dispose of products, services, ideas or experiences to satisfy needs & desires (Solomon et al, 2006). “Consumer behavior is the process whereby individuals decide what, when, where, how & from whom to purchase goods & services”. (Walters & Paul)

Although the definitions given above are various, they all lead to common view that consumer buying behavior is a process of selecting, purchasing & disposing of goods & services according to the needs & wants of the consumers. However, there is a general consensus among the researchers & academics that this process is subject to continual change over time as the purchase characteristics of the customers change due to their physical & psychological needs.

Beauty & Personal Care products encompass a wide range of goods designed for hygiene, grooming & aesthetic enhancement. They hold strong cultural, psychological & economic importance, making them a relevant category for analyzing how demographic factors shape online consumer behaviour.

Recent Facts on Online Consumer Buying Behavior:

S. No.	Fact / Insight	Data / Statistics	Implication for Research
1	Market Growth	Online beauty & personal care market growing at ~11.5% CAGR (2024–2032)	Indicates rapid shift toward online purchasing
2	Price Preference (Millennials)	65.93% Millennials prefer online due to better pricing	Price is a key factor influencing purchase decision
3	Online Penetration (India)	Only ~20% consumers buy beauty products online	Shows untapped market potential
4	Social Media Influence	High impact of influencers & social media platforms	Digital marketing strongly affects buying behavior
5	Value-Conscious Consumers	Preference for value-for-money & multifunctional products	Consumers are becoming price-sensitive
6	Product Category	Skincare ~37% share in beauty purchases	Skincare dominates online demand
7	Demographic Factor	Growth driven by young consumers & rising income (India)	Age & income are key demographic variables

NEED OF THE STUDY:

The Beauty & Personal Care market is booming & one of the fastest growing consumer markets, driven in particular by the Cosmetics & Skin Care segments. The main reason for this strong growth is the generational shift with young consumers entering the market, Female are more in working place & male is also highly concerned about look & appearance. At the same time, this change is reinforced by social media, internationality & e-commerce, which have a lasting effect on buying behavior when it comes to beauty products. Trends from all over the world are spreading & changing the daily beauty & care routine. Growing demand for exclusive beauty products coupled with attractive offers, greater product authenticity & supply chain reliability, it is driving rapid growth in online market.

Online channel split : Horizontal (Amazon, Flipkart), fashion vertical (Myntra) & super vertical (Nykaa, Purplle) players. Fashion vertical players like Myntra is bringing up the tail in the online channel but are focusing on this category as a major revenue driver in the years to come. By this way we can understand that various players/companies are purposely getting enter into this category at the same time consumers are also showing positive interest in

online mode. This study will analyze how people's age, gender, income, education & other personal characteristics affect their online shopping habits for beauty & personal care products.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Substantial research has been conducted on the subject area.

Subhalakshmi R. (2015) conducted a study on customer attitude towards online shopping of cosmetic products in Tirunelveli district with a sample of 316 respondents selected through convenience sampling. Using descriptive statistics & inferential tools (Z-test, ANOVA, correlation, regression), the study found that most online cosmetic buyers were young (21–30), unmarried, highly educated (PG & above), predominantly students or private employees & urban residents. Factor analysis identified web self-efficacy, internet self-efficacy, personal innovativeness, perceived risk, usefulness, ease of use, trust, subjective norms, website features & enjoyment as influencing factors, with web self-efficacy, internet self-efficacy, subjective norms & enjoyment showing stronger impact. Flipkart was the most preferred site & discounts/offers emerged as the key motivator, followed by low price & product variety.

Durrani S. K. (2017) examined youth consumers' preferences for online shopping of lifestyle products (apparel, mobile phones, wristwatches, footwear) in Madhya Pradesh using a descriptive design with 100 college students from Bhopal & Indore (purposive sampling). Findings showed that males (59%) & females (41%) aged 19–25 engaged in occasional rather than frequent purchases. The main motivators were product variety & ease of comparison.

Saluja R. et al. (2018) analyzed online & offline buying behavior in Udaipur using a descriptive design with 305 respondents (convenience sampling). Amazon, Flipkart & Snapdeal were the most preferred sites; males favored electronics & tickets, while females preferred clothes & accessories. Key motivators for online shopping were time saving, 24/7 availability & product variety, while offline shopping was chosen for instant delivery & product inspection. ANOVA results showed a significant gap between consumer expectations & satisfaction after online shopping.

Sharma & Jain (2018) conducted an exploratory study to examine the impact of demographic factors such as age, gender, income, education & profession on online buying behaviour among consumers in Bhopal. The study found that demographic variables significantly influence consumers' online shopping patterns & preferences. Younger, educated & higher-income consumers showed greater inclination towards online purchasing. The authors highlighted the role of awareness, convenience & trust in shaping online buying decisions. However, the study focused on general online shopping & did not examine product-specific behaviour.

Dr. Rambabu Lavuri, Dr. D. Sreeramulu, (2019), in their study, "Personal Care Products: A Study on Women Consumer Buying Behaviour", examines about the buying behaviour of women consumers regarding personal care products. A survey of 172 respondents was carried out with structured questionnaire. They found that demographical factors of respondents having significant mean difference with buying personal care products, products factors like Brand Name, quality, price, Brand Loyalty, Affordability, Recommendations of Sales People & Previous Usage Experiences are significant impact on consumer buying behaviour & influence factors like Brand Ambassadors & Family & Friend references are great impact on buying mode of women respondents.

Prasad A. et al. (2019) studied women's digital shopping behavior for beauty & personal care products using 167 responses (convenience sampling). Factor analysis revealed four

expectation factors—convenience, reliability, flexibility & variety—and two deterrents: delivery authenticity issues & perception problems. Amazon & Nykaa were the most preferred sites, with age as the only demographic influencing expectations. Customer reviews & product information strongly guided purchases, while advertisements had little impact.

Yadav S. & Singh D. (2020) examined the effectiveness of online advertising on consumer buying behavior for clothing & electronics in Kathmandu valley with 203 respondents (convenience sampling). Using regression & other statistical tools, the study found that factors like low cost, offers, variety & attraction had only moderate or neutral influence & overall, online advertisements showed little or no significant impact on consumer purchase behavior due to lack of trust in ad content.

Makhitha & Ngobeni, (2021) examined the influence of demographic factors on perceived risks & attitudes toward online shopping. The study found that age, income & education significantly affect consumers' perceptions of financial, product & privacy risks. Higher perceived risk was associated with a negative attitude toward online shopping. The findings highlight the importance of reducing risk perceptions to improve online purchase behaviour across demographic groups.

Sidra Ishaq, Hammad Badar, Hira Javed, (2021), in their study, "Factors Influencing Female Purchase Behavior for Organic Cosmetic Products in Pakistan" reveals that three factors, health consciousness, environmental consciousness & product quality information, impact significantly consumer behavior for organic cosmetics. **Puzari, Thummar & Saduwala (2023)** conducted an empirical investigation into customer satisfaction in the context of online shopping & observed a substantial level of consumer awareness & participation in digital commerce.

Their findings indicated that an overwhelming majority of respondents had prior experience with online purchases, reflecting the growing acceptance & penetration of e-commerce in India. The study further attributed this shift in purchasing behaviour to evolving consumer lifestyles & increased internet accessibility.

Website security emerged as a critical determinant influencing consumers' inclination toward online shopping platforms. **Singh, Chaturvedi, Mittal & Mittal (2023)** examined the role of artificial intelligence in shaping online customer satisfaction through a multiple regression framework.

The study identified AI-driven product recommendations, personalized shopping interfaces, real-time customer interaction & chatbot assistance as significant contributors to enhanced consumer satisfaction. The results underscored the increasing relevance of intelligent technologies in strengthening customer engagement & improving overall online shopping experiences. The study by **Indiani et al. (2024)** investigates the moderating role of demographic factors in online purchase behavior using the Theory of Planned Behavior framework. The research is based on a sample of 450 online consumers & data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The findings reveal that purchase intention, trust & eWOM significantly influence actual buying behavior. Demographic variables (age, gender, income) were found to moderate the relationship between trust & purchase behavior, but not between intention & behavior. The study highlights that only around 30% of consumers convert intention into actual purchase, emphasizing the importance of trust in e-commerce.

Sonia (2024) studied "Consumer Behavior in Online Shopping: A Comparative Analysis of Generational Differences" uses a quantitative research approach to examine behavioral

differences among Millennials, Generation X & Baby Boomers. The study is based on comparative analysis of generational cohorts using survey-based data (sample size not explicitly specified in the paper). The analysis focuses on variables such as trust, perceived risk, shopping motivation & payment preferences. Findings reveal that Millennials show higher online shopping frequency & are influenced by social media, while Generation X relies on reviews & brand trust & Baby Boomers emphasize security & prefer traditional payment methods. The study concludes that consumer behavior significantly varies across generations, requiring targeted marketing strategies.

Dubey P. (2025) examines customer buying behaviour in online shopping with a focus on electronic goods. The study identifies key determinants such as convenience, trust, security & accessibility as major influences on consumer decision-making. Using primary data through questionnaires & interviews, the research highlights the growing preference for online platforms due to ease of comparison & time-saving benefits. Overall, it provides a useful but largely descriptive understanding of online consumer behaviour in the electronics segment.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Objectives of study:

1. To study the impact of demographic factors on online buying behaviour of beauty & personal care products. The demographic variables included age, gender, education, profession, marital status, family income & place of residence.
2. To study consumer satisfaction & repeat purchase behaviour across different demographic groups.

Objective: 1. To study the impact of demographic factors on online buying behaviour of beauty & personal care products. The demographic variables included age, gender, education, profession, marital status, family income & place of residence.

Sampling: The study was conducted in Indore city of state Madhya Pradesh. A sample of 150 respondents was selected, comprising regular buyers of Beauty & Personal Care products through online platforms. The respondents were chosen using the simple random sampling method.

Tools for data collection & analysis: Secondary data were collected from sources like Internet, books, journals, magazines etc. Five-point scale questionnaire was used for primary data collection. The data were tabulated in Excel sheet & analyzed using regression analysis.

Hypothesis:

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of demographic factors—age, gender, education, profession, marital status & income—on the online buying behaviour of beauty & personal care products.

The above null hypothesis was tested & results were drawn.

Findings & Discussions:

Table 1

Model Summary ^b						
Model	R	R	Adjusted	Std. Error	Change Statistics	Durbin-

		Square	R Square	of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	Watson
1	.939 ^a	.881	.876	.367	.881	176.998	6	143	.000	.337
a. Predictors: (Constant), income of the family, marital status, age of the respondents, profession of the respondents, education of the respondents, gender of the respondents										
b. Dependent Variable: PLACE OF RESIDENCE										

The regression model assessing the effect of demographic factors—age, gender, education, profession, marital status & family income—on the dependent variable (Place of Residence, as a proxy for online buying behaviour) shows a high explanatory power ($R = 0.939$, $R^2 = 0.881$). This means that 88.1% of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by these demographic predictors. The model is statistically significant ($F(6,143) = 176.998$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that, collectively, the demographic factors have a significant association with online buying behaviour. Based on these results, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, as demographic characteristics meaningfully influence the outcome variable in this study.

Table 2

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	143.386	6	23.898	176.998	.000 ^b
	Residual	19.307	143	.135		
	Total	162.693	149			

The ANOVA results confirm that the regression model is highly significant ($F(6,143) = 176.998$, $p < 0.001$). This indicates that, taken together, the demographic variables—age, gender, education, profession, marital status & family income—explain a statistically significant portion of the variance in the dependent variable (Place of Residence). Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, supporting the conclusion that these demographic factors collectively influence online buying behaviour of beauty & personal care products.

Table 3

Co efficient ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.353	.121		-2.928	.004
	Age of the respondents	-.292	.138	-.293	-2.112	.036
	Gender of the respondents	.392	.277	.186	1.416	.159

Education of the respondents	1.041	.138	.902	7.565	.000
Profession of the respondents	.534	.118	.466	4.518	.000
Marital status	.888	.265	.420	3.346	.001
Income of the family	-1.084	.144	-.714	-7.541	.000
a. Dependent Variable: PLACE OF RESIDENCE					

The regression analysis results indicate that certain demographic factors significantly influence the place of residence of respondents. Among these, education level ($\beta = 0.902$, $p < 0.001$), profession ($\beta = 0.466$, $p < 0.001$), marital status ($\beta = 0.420$, $p = 0.001$), income of the family ($\beta = -0.714$, $p < 0.001$) & age ($\beta = -0.293$, $p = 0.036$) were found to be statistically significant predictors. Gender, however, did not show a significant effect ($p = 0.159$). The model explains a substantial portion of the variance ($F = 176.998$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting a strong relationship between the selected demographic variables & the place of residence.

Table 4

Residuals Statistics ^a					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	1.13	4.33	2.91	.981	150
Residual	-.888	.632	.000	.360	150
Std. Predicted Value	-1.815	1.450	.000	1.000	150
Std. Residual	-2.418	1.720	.000	.980	150
a. Dependent Variable: PLACE OF RESIDENCE					

The residual statistics indicate that the predicted values for the dependent variable Place of Residence range from 1.13 to 4.33, with a mean of 2.91 & a standard deviation of 0.981, showing a moderate spread around the mean prediction. Residuals, representing the difference between observed & predicted values, vary from -0.888 to 0.632, with a mean close to zero, confirming that the model is unbiased in its predictions. The standardized predicted values range from -1.815 to 1.450, while the standardized residuals range from -2.418 to 1.720, both within acceptable limits, indicating no extreme outliers. Overall, these results suggest that the regression model demonstrates stable predictions without significant deviations.

Objective: 2. To study consumer satisfaction & repeat purchase behaviour across different demographic groups.

Tools for data collection & analysis: The qualitative analysis was conducted using Thematic Analysis to identify key themes related to consumer satisfaction & repeat purchase behavior across different demographic groups. Data Sources typically used tools such as Open-ended questionnaire responses & Consumer comments & feedback

Analysis:

The qualitative analysis reveals that consumer satisfaction & repeat purchase behaviour for online Beauty & Personal Care (BPC) products vary notably across demographic segments. These variations are influenced by differences in expectations, purchasing motivations, digital familiarity & perceived risk.

(a) Age-wise Analysis: Younger consumers exhibit higher satisfaction levels due to their familiarity with digital platforms, ease of navigation & responsiveness to online discounts, influencer reviews & fast delivery. They show strong repeat purchase behaviour, often driven by brand loyalty & promotional offers. In contrast, older consumers demonstrate moderate satisfaction, primarily influenced by product quality & trust in the platform. Their repeat purchases are more cautious & depend on prior positive experiences.

(b) Gender-wise Analysis: Female consumers generally report higher satisfaction & repeat purchase intent, as BPC products align closely with their routine needs. They actively engage with product reviews, ratings & return policies before making repeat purchases.

Male consumers, while increasingly participating in online BPC purchases, tend to show lower repeat frequency, often driven by necessity rather than brand exploration.

(c) Income-wise Analysis: Consumers from higher income groups display greater satisfaction due to access to premium brands, better service quality & flexible return policies. Their repeat purchase behaviour is influenced by brand trust & perceived value.

Middle-income consumers are price-sensitive & highly responsive to discounts & offers, which strongly affects their satisfaction & likelihood of repeat purchases.

(d) Education-wise Analysis: Highly educated consumers show greater awareness & informed decision-making, leading to higher satisfaction when product information is transparent & reliable. Their repeat purchase behaviour depends on consistency in quality & service.

Lower education groups rely more on peer recommendations & platform reputation, which influences satisfaction & repeat buying intentions.

(e) Occupation-wise Analysis: Working professionals demonstrate high repeat purchase behaviour due to convenience, time-saving benefits & subscription-based models.

Students & homemakers show selective repeat purchase behaviour, influenced by affordability, peer influence & promotional campaigns.

Conclusion: The study highlights that a uniform marketing strategy may not be effective across all demographic groups. Online BPC retailers should adopt demographic-specific strategies to enhance satisfaction & encourage repeat purchases.

LIMITATION & SCOPE OF STUDY:

The study was conducted in selected city of Madhya Pradesh with a sample of 150 respondents. The findings of study may not be generalized for other cities of the state & country. Further studies can be done on large sample size & comparative studies between metro Vs non-metro cities can also be done in future.

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